

ICCM24

24TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS

caelestis

Hyperconnected simulation ecosystem supporting probabilistic design
and predictive manufacturing of next generation aircraft structures –
CAELESTIS Project

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- ✓ INTRODUCTION TO CAELESTIS PROJECT
- ✓ OBJECTIVES
- ✓ MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY
- ✓ EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS
- ✓ CONCLUSIONS

Introduction to CAELESTIS project

Driver....

Adopting a new breed of aircraft is essential for reaching climate neutrality by 2050

According to the aeronautics community, **virtual engineering** has a big potential to be the **key enabling technology** in achieving these objectives and making **zero carbon aviation** a reality.

The chief aim is to develop a robust and secure **digital ecosystem**, utilizing **simulation-driven design** to innovate a **new manufacturing methodology** able to transform the European aircraft industry – and reduce emissions.

11 partners

8 countries

Coordinated by:

May 2022

October 2025

We are a multi-sector **Innovation and Technology Centre**, that develops **R&D&i activities** and provides **technological services** in the fields of:

AIMEN is in O Porriño
(15km to **Vigo**) **Galicia, Spain.**

COMPTech

Advanced Composites Technologies

Advanced Composites Manufacturing

Additive Manufacturing

Smart Materials

Monitoring – Control

Automated / Robotized

Digitalization

(Process and Product)

Sustainable Materials and Manufacturing

Analysis and Testing

40 Researchers
12 PhD

Projects:
17 Nationals
18 European

CAELESTIS develops an **end-to-end Interoperable Simulation Ecosystem (ISE)** that will perform **multidirectional dataflow** across the aircraft value chain **linking product design and distributed engineering teams' CAD-CAE tools**, to accelerate the design and engineering optimization of disruptive aircraft and engine configurations.

caelestis Interoperable Simulation Ecosystem

Product/process optimization ↑ ↓ Massive simulation campaigns

↑ ↓ Product / Process data

Automation and Digitalization of Composites Manufacturing (AFP, RTM)

HIGH PERFORMANCE COMPUTING

High-Fidelity simulation workflows

Machine learning algorithms

OBJECTIVES

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This work is focused on the AFP process parametrization and the digitalization of the dry preform using on-line monitoring systems (*digital twin*)

Objectives:

- To understand the effect of the **AFP process parameters** on the dry fiber preform quality (*tape adhesion*) and, at the end, on the composite mechanical performance.
- To analyze the influence of AFP parameters on **resin permeability** behavior, and, at the end, on the RTM processing performance.
- To **digitalize the dry-fiber preform** manufacturing based on **on-line quality control systems** (*SmartHub tool*).

To give input from experimental data to process modelling / digital twin – data workflow
To contribute to the CAELESTIS ISE (interoperable simulation ecosystem)

Materials and methodology

Carbon dry fiber preform by AFP (Automated Fiber Placement) and RTM (Resin Transfer Molding)

Outlet Guide Vane (OGV)

Defects on dry fiber preform during AFP

Figure 2: Gap/Overlap Actual Representation.

Figure 6: Wrinkle Actual Representation.

Figure 15: Twist Actual Representation.

Figure 13: Fold Actual Representation.

Harik, R., Saidy, C., Williams, S. J., Gurdal, Z., & Grimsley, B. (2018).

Quality control on-line monitoring systems:

- ✓ Thermal camera - temperature measurements
- ✓ Profilometry - fiber layup topography map

AFP (Automated Fibre Placement)

TeXtreme

Ref 5172: 194 UD IMS65 VO /25:194 SPREAD TOW
Toho Tenax E IMS65 E23 24K 830tex
Binder: Spunfab® PA1206 6 g/m2

AFP deposition of UD tape

Materials and Methodology

RTM (Resin Transfer Molding)

HexFlow RTM6 Epoxy resin

RTM machine

AFP head and laser heating system (VCSEL)

Profilometer
Thermal Camera
VCSELS
(High power laser)

Control Input		Control Result		Laser	
Enable	Level	IR Power [W]	Clip	OK	
1	2.100		200		
2	2.95		190		
3	2.90		180		
4	2.85		170		
5	2.80		160		
6	2.75		150		
7	2.70		140		
8	2.65		130		
9	2.60		120		
10	2.55		110		
11	2.50		100		
12	2.45		90		

Heating: IR VCSEL system (2,4 kW):

- ✓ 12 independent heating zones (*adjustable power*)
 - ✓ 5 zones were selected to concentrate heating on CF tape (*1 inch width*)
- Total power: 1000W*
- ✓ Process monitoring (*thermal camera*)

Main parameters that affect the AFP process:

Factor	Measurement unit	Variable type
Head/roll pressure	N	Quantitative
Deposition velocity	mm/s	Quantitative
Heating source power	W	Quantitative
Fiber areal weight	g/m ²	Quantitative
Tape thickness	mm	Quantitative
Binder type	-	Qualitative
Head/roll material	-	Qualitative
Lay-up sequence	-	Qualitative
Font position, inclination	mm, °	Quantitative
Stagger	mm	Quantitative

Study: Effect of AFP selected variables on dry fiber preform properties:

Factor	Effect	Unit	Type	Evaluation
Head/roll pressure	Tape thickness	mm	Quantitative	Direct measurement
	Preform compaction	m ²	Quantitative	Permeability test
Deposition velocity	Manufacturing time	s	Quantitative	Direct measurement
	Tape temperature	°C	Quantitative	Pyrometers and thermal camera
Heating input	Tape temperature	°C	Quantitative	Power consumption

Tape-by-tape consolidation (adhesion) – dry fiber preform compaction

Dry Carbon Fiber AFP process parameters – SoA and AIMEN expertise

Heat Source	Dry Fiber	Heat power (W)	Temperature at nit point (°C)	Compaction force (N)	Deposition speed (mm/s)		[Ref]
					1ª	Other	
Laser 3 kW	Carbon fiber + epoxy/ thermoplastic binder	-	200	446	-	400	[6]
Laser	Carbon fiber 24K (weight in área: 194 g/m ²) + thermoplastic binder	800	200 (800 m/s)	200	400	800	[5]
			320 (400 m/s)				
Laser 3 kW	Carbon fiber + binder	200	200	446	-	400	[4]
		357	300				
Hot Gas Torch	-	-	176	311	25,4	100	[3]
Laser	PRISM TX1100	-	160	160	-	200	[7]
Laser 6 kW	Carbon fiber	-	-	446	-	100,200,400,800	[8]
Laser	Carbon fiber 24K UD (weight in área: 194 g/m ²) + thermoplastic binder	800	250	200	-	100	[9]
IR halogen lamp	Carbon fiber	360	110	-	-	850	[10]
Laser	Carbon fiber (HFW160PA)	-	160	160	-	200	[11]
Laser	Carbon fiber 24K Ud (weight in area;:194 g/m ²) + thermoplastic binder	800	250	200	-	1000	[12]

Determination of process window

The DOE parameter levels (V, Pres, Pow) have been adjusted based on the AIMEN AFP equipment, our expertise and the experimental previous works.

Selection of parameters levels to perform AFP DOE

Factor	Measurement unit	Min	Max	Variable type
Head/roll pressure	N	250	500	Quantitative
Deposition velocity	mm/s	100	400	Quantitative
Heating source power (5 zones)	W	100 (10%)	400 (40%)	Quantitative

- Pressure < 250 N results in pulling/dragging effect of the dry CF (no adhesion)
- Velocities > 400 mm/s surpasses the AFP head reliability with dry CF (velocity not uniform for the short sample length)
- Power > 400 W makes the fibers and binder burn.

Peeling test

- Quantitative evaluation of adhesion between layers using an adapted set-up for peeling test [1-2]:
 - ✓ Able to measure the adhesion between layers (*there are not standards for dry fiber*)
 - ✓ No large quantities of material are required for this analysis (*usually requires to manufacture a complete laminate to be injected and later analyzed*)
- The samples have been made using 4 CF layers.
- Peeling length: 135 ± 5 mm.
- Peeling test was performed by holding 1 or 2 layers (no difference found)

Figura 2. Carga (N) vs desplazamiento (mm) Grupo4.

Darcy's Law can provide the **preforms' permeability** (in-plane) along the linear flow direction (k):

- x_{ff} is the flow front position at the injection time t_{ff}
- Φ is the porosity of the preform
- μ is the viscosity of the injected fluid that is used for the tests (*calibrated oil*)
- ΔP is the pressure difference between the inlet and the outlet locations (constant)

$$K = - \frac{x_{ff}^2 \cdot \Phi \cdot \mu}{2 \cdot \Delta P \cdot t_{ff}}$$

Preforms 2mm thickness, 11 layers, layup 0°

Experimental Results - AFP parametrization

Samples	Speed (mm/s)	Power (W)	Pressure (N)	Peeling strength (N/m)	ST. Dev.
1	100	100	250	No adhesion	
2	400	100	250	No adhesion	
3	100	400	250	77,6 ±13,5	13,5
4	400	400	250	29,7 ±12,1	12,1
5	100	100	500	No adhesion	
6	100	100	500	No adhesion	
7	100	400	500	123,0 ±14,7	14,7
8	400	400	500	71,2 ±8,1	8,1
15	250	250	375	44,1 ±2,2	2,2

The higher peel strength values occur:

- ✓ At higher power
- ✓ At lower speed

Both parameters have influence on the temperature input on the tape.

It seems that pressure is the lowest influent parameter.

No adhesion:
T << 60 °C

Highest adhesion:
T = 180-170 °C

Thermal camera data on real time

TeXtreme

Binder: Spunfab® PA1206 6 g/m2
Tm: 160-170 °C

Sample	Permeability (m^2) $\times(10^{-12})$				Peeling Strength (N/m)
	k_{z1} (zone 1)	k_{z2} (zone 2)	k_{z3} (zone 3)	Mean	
# 3	7,0354	8,1455	9,1325	8,1045	77,6
# 4	10,204	9,8208	26,6957	10,5661	29,7
# 7	4,2073	9,6302	-	6,9188	123,0

- Race-tracking (*fast resin channels*) have been observed in all the samples due to the gaps between tapes.
- The permeability has been estimated discarding the fast tracks.

Reference permeability values using similar material/process were not found. Some UD-CF studies showed values between $6-20 \times 10^{-12} m^2$.

- ✓ Higher peel strength (higher compaction) results in lower permeability.
- ✓ Less dry fiber preform compaction results in a better permeability.

Low dry fiber preform compaction means better permeability but... how this can affect during RTM in the %resin?

Experimental Results - AFP on-line quality control

A profilometer was installed in the AFP head to scan every ply of the preform.

**Profilometer
MicroEpsilon
LLT3010-50/BL**

**Profilometer
laser line**

Profilometer scanning process is carried out tow by tow to generate a 3D point cloud of each ply
(see video)

Each scanned tow individually by the profilometer is located next to the next one to be displayed as a whole ply.

- Tow with a 5 mm **gap** defect in both sides.

Gaps

- Tow with a 5mm **overlap** defect in both sides.

Overlaps

Complete ply with artificial 5 mm **overlap** defects.

To match AFP-fry fiber defects with any possible RTM defect, it is necessary to reference the 3D point cloud scan of each ply with the robot manufacturing trajectories.

Robot manufacturing trajectories for one ply

3D point cloud scan of one ply overlapped with robot trajectories

Thermal camera that provides thermal images for off-axis temperature measurement

Thermal Camera
FLIR A70

Thermal image of the AFP process

Thermal data analysis of the AFP process:

- Plot 1 shows the profile temperature of one tow while laser is ON (*area within the red circle is the relevant*)
- Plot 2 shows the profile temperature of several consecutive tows.
- Plot 3 represents the average temperature of the relevant area of all tows for each layer of the whole preform.

Complete information for AFP on-line quality control:

Overlapping Profilometer + Thermal camera + Robot position

“SmartHub” TOOL: Complete collection of information of AFP manufacturing (VIDEO)

Experimental Results - Demonstrator manufacturing

DEMONSTRATOR

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

- ✓ The AFP parameter that has more influence in the compaction (peel strength) of the dry fiber is the heating input (resulted from laser power and velocity).
- ✓ The optimum AFP process $T > T_m$ (*binder activation*) $T < T_{degradation}$
- ✓ The higher permeabilities occur at the lower compaction of the dry preform.
- ✓ The “SmartHub” tool allow us the on-line quality control and manufacturing data analysis

On-going next steps:

- ✓ To study the effect of the dry fiber preform quality on the RTM process and on the mechanical properties of the final laminates.
- ✓ To give input to the CAELESTIS simulation workflow

Sensorized RTM mold

Resin flow front

- Pressure sensor
- Cure degree sensor
- Resin Arrival + T sensor

Thanks for your attention!

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